

NFDI 4
BIODIVERSITY
BIODIVERSITY, ECOLOGY & ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

Assessment of NFDI4Biodiversity involvement in cross-cutting activities and recommendations for additional focus areas

Strategic Report for Milestone 2.1.3

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Executive Summary

NFID4Biodiversity is very active in most of the Task Forces (TF), Jours Fixes (JF), Sections and their subgroups, working groups (WG), work packages, and other committees of the NFDI-wide landscape.

35 people from NFID4Biodiversity are involved in 40 of the 45 groups analyzed in this report.

Notable high involvement happens in the Section Common Infrastructures, in particular in its working groups Data Integration, Long-term Archival, Multi-Cloud, and Persistent Identifiers, as well as in the JF Management, the group on Fair Data Spaces. The strong involvement of NFID4Biodiversity in the BASE4NFDI proposal process led to participation in the following projects: IAM4NFDI, PID4NFDI, TS4NFDI, and Jupyter4NFDI..

Groups without NFID4Biodiversity involvement are:

- From TF Tools:
 - Subgroup File Sharing Cloud
- From Section Common Infrastructures:
 - WG Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DSAI)
 - WG Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN)
 - WG Infrastructure and Data Security (IDS)
- From Section (Meta)Data, Terminologies, Provenance:
 - WG Search and Harvesting

Groups with low NFID4Biodiversity involvement are:

- TF User Research
- From Section Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects
 - TF Data Protection
- From Section Training & Education
- DALIA Knowledge Base "FAIR data usage and supply"

Although NFID4Biodiversity is overall very well involved in the various sections, a survey in TA2 suggested stronger activities in various fields of work in the "Common Infrastructures" and "Training and Education" sections. Based on this feedback, further measures for activities are coordinated, for example in the context of the Strategic Advisory Board (SAB).

Introduction

NFDI4Biodiversity is a well-established consortium within NFDI. Thanks to the predecessor project GFBio, NFDI4Biodiversity could rely on a solid foundation of well-connected partners, tools, and procedures to ensure a smooth start in the NFDI landscape.

With its leading role, NFDI4Biodiversity and its partners are well-connected within the NFDI ecosystem. These involvements however were primarily steered by the interests and motivations of the individuals and not so much by an overarching NFDI4Biodiversity-wide strategy

So the goal of this report was to qualitatively analyze the involvement of people connected to NFDI4Biodiversity in the many working groups that exist on an NFDI-wide level. This allows us to see the areas where we have a strong standing as well as identify the groups with no or little representation from NFDI4Biodiversity. The results can then be used as a basis for a strategic decision process in which groups to increase our involvement, as they might be decisive for the standing of NFDI4Biodiversity within NFDI.

Methods

For this report, we analyzed which persons from NFDI4Biodiversity are active in which NFDI-wide Task Forces (TF), Jours Fixe (JF), Sections and their subgroups (SG), working groups (WG), work packages (WP) as well as Base4NFDI services, other committees and governing bodies. In the following, we will use the term working group to encompass all of the aforementioned bodies.

In order to properly quantify the level of engagement of a person in any given working group, their involvement was scored on a numeric system from 0 (not active) to 3 (lead of the group).

Number	Category	Explanation
3	Lead	(Co)Lead of the section, WG, Task Force
2	Active participation	Attending Meetings, active contribution to the group's work
1	Participation	Attending Meetings, passive listener
0	Not active	No involvement in the group's work

Table 1: Levels of Involvement

This report represents the state of involvement at the end of August 2023.

Evaluated groups

A description of the goals, the target audiences and the meeting frequencies of the task forces and jours fixes can be found at NFDI Community Meeting page¹.

Task Forces

TF Evaluation and Reporting (TFER) (*formerly known as TF Monitoring*)

TF User Research

TF Tools

- ~~Subgroup AA~~ (*superseded by Base4NFDI project IAM4NFDI*)
- Subgroup Helpdesk
- Subgroup Projectmanagement
- Subgroup Rocket.Chat
- Subgroup Data Management Planning
- Subgroup File Sharing Cloud

Jours Fixes

JF Speakers

JF Communication

JF Finance

JF Management (*formerly known as JF Administration*)

JF Sections

Sections

Common Infrastructures (section-infra)²:

- WG Data Integration (DI)
- WG Data Management Planning (DMP)
- WG Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DSAI)
- WG Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN)
- WG Identity and Access Management (IAM)
- WG Infrastructure and Data Security (IDS)
- WG Long-term Archival (LTA)
- WG Multi-Cloud (MC)
- WG Persistent Identifiers (PID)
- WG Research Software Engineering (RSE)

Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (section-ELSA)³:

¹ <https://www.nfdi.de/community-meetings/?lang=en>

² <https://www.nfdi.de/section-infra/?lang=en>

³ <https://www.nfdi.de/section-elsa/?lang=en>

- TF Data Protection

(Meta)Data, Terminologies, Provenance (section-metadata)⁴:

- WG Cookbooks, Guidance and Best Practice
- WG Terminology Services
- WG Ontology Harmonization and Mapping
- WG Search and Harvesting
- WG Knowledge Graphs

Training & Education (section-edutrain)⁵:

- WP1: Target group and needs analysis
- WP2: Inventory of materials
- WP3: Development of a modular and scalable concept
- WP4: Development of joint multidimensional teaching materials and building a Knowledge Base
- WP5: Training formats and certificate course
- ~~WP6: Quality assurance and evaluation~~ *(has been merged with WP4)*
- WP7: Networking and Outreach
- WP8: Error culture in science

Industry Engagement (section-industry)⁶

Other groups

Consortia Assembly⁷

Base4NFDI Proposal WG⁸ and funded Basic Services

FAIR Data Spaces⁹

DALIA Knowledge Base "FAIR data usage and supply"¹⁰

Reporting and Evaluation Table

Starting with all of the involvements of people that we were already aware of, we created a spreadsheet to denote each person's involvement in the different working groups. We also asked all of the project participants on several occasions to further report any work that we might not have been aware of. In total, we got the information from 35 people that represent NFDI4Biodiversity in one or more NFDI working groups. A summarized table for the different working groups can be found in Appendix A.

⁴ <https://www.nfdi.de/section-meta/?lang=en>

⁵ <https://www.nfdi.de/section-edutrain/?lang=en>

⁶ <https://www.nfdi.de/section-industry-engagement/?lang=en>

⁷ <https://www.nfdi.de/association/?lang=en#vereinsorgane>

⁸ <https://base4nfdi.de/>

⁹ <https://www.nfdi.de/fair-data-spaces/?lang=en>

¹⁰ <https://dalia.education/>

Additionally we also keep track of all of the publications produced by the different working groups where people from NFDI4Biodiversity were listed as co-authors as well as the proposals for basic services with NFDI4Biodiversity involvement that were submitted during the first two rounds of Base4NFDI.

Results

In total 35 people from NFDI4Biodiversity reported their participation in any of the groups. These people come from 13 different institutions and are involved in 40 out of the 45 still active groups that were evaluated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1: Engagement of NFDI4Biodiversity consortium members within the NFDI in numbers: Persons (Box 1) from diverse partner institutions (Box 2) acting as delegates or with functions in NFDI groups, total number of NFDI groups with NFDI4Biodiversity engagement (Box 3), number of NFDI publications the members contributed to (Box 4) and number of basic service proposals with involvement of NFDI4Biodiversity partner institutions (Box 5).

Groups with high involvement

An individual participation in a subgroup was counted as participation for the overarching section or task force. Therefore sections with a large number of subgroups, i.e. Common Infrastructures and Training & Education have a high level of participation. But in particular within Common Infrastructures, there is significant involvement in the working groups Data Integration, Long-term Archival, Multi-Cloud, and Persistent Identifiers. Furthermore, the section lead is filled by an NFDI4Biodiversity partner (Fig. 2).

The working group for the Base4NFDI Proposal saw active contributions from 7 people from our project. Moreover, NFDI4Biodiversity is a driving force in the Management and Communication Circle, the TF Evaluation & Reporting, and in the Fair Data Spaces project (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2: Top five groups and areas of NFDI4Biodiversity engagement within the NFDI, depicting the number of people involved as well as the main outputs or achievements.

Groups with low involvement

There are currently 5 groups in which NFDI4Biodiversity is not represented at all:

- TF Tools: Subgroup File Sharing Cloud
- section-infra: WG Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DSAI)
- section-infra WG Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN)
- section-infra WG Infrastructure and Data Security (IDS)
- section-metadata: WG Search and Harvesting

In the following groups, NFDI4Biodiversity is only represented with a single regular participant:

- TF User Research
- section-ELSA: TF Data Protection
- DALIA Knowledge Base "FAIR data usage and supply"

Groups with involvement where further engagement is desired

In parallel to the feedback from the NFDI4Biodiversity members regarding their involvements in the various NFDI wide working groups, we asked participants in the "2connect" task area about groups that could use further engagement despite an already solid presence of NFDI4Biodiversity representatives. This feedback namely was from:

The following points were raised in the responses:

Section "Common Infrastructures":

- More engagement in the working groups Data Integration, Multi Cloud and Long-term Archival (LTA) would be desirable.
- A reorientation towards the Data Mesh concept would be useful for NFDI4Biodiversity.
- The Working Group "Long Term Archival (LTA)" would need further support from colleagues with technical competency (TA4), in particular in regard to the NFDI-wide RDC-LTA concept and PID technologies.

Section "Training and Education":

- Due to some colleagues leaving, the group is missing some power of action and the potential for synergies can not be fully utilized. More support is desirable.

Basic service proposals

As mentioned above, NFDI4Biodiversity was strongly involved in the process of preparing the proposal for Base4NFDI, a union of consortia committed to the establishment of NFDI-wide basic services. After Base4NFDI took up its work in March 2023, several NFDI4Biodiversity partners were involved in submitting proposals for Basic services. In the first round of funding, six partners were involved in the following four out of a total of six proposals:

- DMP4NFDI (Basic Service for Data Management Plans)
- IAM4NFDI (Identity and Access Management)
- PID4NFDI (Persistent Identifier Services)
- TS4NFDI (Terminology Services)

In the first round, only the IAM4NFDI proposal was accepted for funding for the initialisation phase. In the second funding round, also PID4NFDI and TS4NFDI were accepted. Furthermore, IAM4NFDI was accepted for the second phase (integration) of basic service establishment. In the third funding round, one NFDI4Biodiversity partner was involved in the proposal Jupyter4NFDI (A Central JupyterHub for the NFDI). The other two proposals were without NFDI4Biodiversity involvement.

Other outputs

There are 13 publications that were published in the context of NFDI that were co-authored by people involved in NFDI4Biodiversity. The complete list of these publications can be seen in Appendix B.

Apart from the involvement in the diverse consortia-overarching groups and activities, NFDI4Biodiversity pursues common interests with other NFDI consortia, both single-domain and cross-domain¹¹. These result in a range of different activities and outputs, such as shared services, jointly organized events, and trainings (Fig. 3). Naturally, cross-consortia collaborations most often arise with other natural and life science consortia that share sub-communities but are not limited to these. Joint activities are initialised either by joint partners, user needs, or regular local engagement.

¹¹ Amelung, L. et al. (2023). Collaborative work in NFDI. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8296724>

Fig. 3: Examples of cross-consortia collaborations, showing the number of shared partners and the different forms of collaboration.

Appendix A - Table of Involvements

	# of people involved	# of institutions involved	level of involvement (summed)	level of involvement (normalized)
<i>Task Forces</i>				
TF Evaluation and Reporting (TFER)	4	2	8	2
TF User Research	1	1	1	1
TF Tools	3	2	3	1
Subgroup Helpdesk	2	2	3	1,5
Subgroup Projectmanagement	2	1	2	1
Subgroup Rocket.Chat	2	1	2	1
Subgroup Data Management Planning	2	1	4	2
Subgroup File Sharing Cloud	0	0	0	
<i>Jours Fixes</i>				
JF Speakers	2	2	4	2
JF Communication	1	1	3	3
JF Finance	3	2	6	2
JF Management	3	1	7	2,3
JF Sections	1	1	2	2
<i>Sections</i>				
Common Infrastructures (section-infra):	14	10	29	2,1
WG Data Integration (DI)	3	3	7	2,3
WG Data Management Planning (DMP)	2	1	4	2
WG Data Science and Artificial Intelligence (DSAI)	0	0	0	
WG Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELN)	0	0	0	
WG Identity and Access Management (IAM)	1	1	2	2
WG Infrastructure and Data Security (IDS)	0	0	0	
WG Long-term Archival (LTA)	3	2	6	2
WG Multi-Cloud (MC)	4	4	8	2
WG Persistent Identifiers (PID)	2	2	5	2,5
WG Research Software Engineering (RSE)	1	1	2	2

Ethical, Legal and Social Aspects (section-ELSA):	3	2	4	1,3
TF Data Protection	1	1	1	1
(Meta)Data, Terminologies, Provenance (section-metadata):	2	2	4	2
WG Cookbooks, Guidance and Best Practice	1	1	2	2
WG Terminology Services	1	1	3	3
WG Ontology Harmonization and Mapping	2	2	3	1,5
WG Search and Harvesting	0	0	0	
WG Knowledge Graphs	1	1	2	2
Training & Education (section-edutrain):	5	3	10	2
WP1: Target group and needs analysis	1	1	2	2
WP2: Inventory of materials	1	1	2	2
WP3: Development of a modular and scalable concept	1	1	2	2
WP4: Development of joint multidimensional teaching materials and building a Knowledge Base	1	1	2	2
WP5: Training formats and certificate course	1	1	2	2
WP7: Networking and Outreach	1	1	2	2
WP8: Error culture in science	1	1	2	2
Industry Engagement (section-industry)	2	2	4	2
<i>Basic Services</i>				
IAM4NFDI	1	1	2	2
PID4NFDI	4	4	9	2
TS4NFDI	1	1	2	2
<i>Other groups</i>				
Consortia Assembly	2	2	4	2
Base4NFDI Proposal WG	7	5	14	2
FAIR Data Spaces	2	2	6	3
DALIA Knowledge Base "FAIR data usage and supply"	1	1	1	1

Appendix B - Publications

NFDI in General

Amelung, L. et al. (2023). Collaborative work in NFDI. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8296724>

TF Evaluation and Reporting

Amelung, L. et al. (2023). White Paper: Interim Report Reference. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7688728>

Amelung, L. et al. (2023). White Paper: Umgang mit Zielen der BLV als Grundlage für die Strukturevaluation. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8191842>

JF Speakers

Ebert, B. et al. (2021). NFDI Cross-cutting Topics Workshop Report. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4593769>

Section Common Infrastructures

Diepenbroek, M.; Schimmler, S. & Ebert, B. (2021). Sektionskonzept Common Infrastructures zur Einrichtung einer Sektion im Verein Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) e.V. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5607489>

WG Data Integration (DI)

Seeger, B.; Henrich, A.; Papenbrock, T. & Riehle, D. (2022). NFDI Data Integration. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6518770>

WG Long-term Archival (LTA)

Bach, F. et al. (2022). Concept for Setting up an LTA Working Group in the NFDI Section "Common Infrastructures". Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6451455>

WG Multi-Cloud (MC)

Dieckmann, M. et al. (2022). NFDI Multi Cloud concept. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6510727>

WG Persistent Identifiers (PID)

Enke, H. et al. (2022). Data management planning: Concept for Setting up a Working Group in the NFDI Section Common Infrastructures. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6499326>

Section (Meta)Data, Terminologies, Provenance

WG Terminology Services

Anders, I. et al. (2022). Terminology Services - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6759324>

WG Ontology Harmonization and Mapping

Anders, I. et al. (2022). Ontology Harmonization and Mapping - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6726518>

WG Knowledge Graphs

Stocker, M. et al. (2023). Knowledge Graphs - Working Group Charter (NFDI section-metadata). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7228954>

Section Training & Education

Pelz, P., et al. (2022). Working Group Charter Training Infrastructures. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6478697>